

The Numismatic Chronicle 178 Offprint

The Pious Son.
On the Restored Denarius Issue Signed by Hadrian

by

BERNHARD E. WOYTEK

LONDON
THE ROYAL NUMISMATIC SOCIETY
2018

The Pious Son. On the Restored Denarius Issue Signed by Hadrian¹

BERNHARD E. WOYTEK

[PLATE 15]

IN THIS paper, a new interpretation of an exceedingly rare coin type of Hadrian will be offered. This restored denarius type, struck in honour of the Divus Traianus, was discovered in the 18th century, but has received little attention since and has never been understood properly. We will first provide a description of the type and comprehensive information on the two specimens known, of which just one can currently be traced; then we will proceed to a discussion of the images and try to contextualise the issue.

Obv. DIVVS TRAIANVS PATE[R AVGVSTVS]

Laureate, undraped bust of the Divus Traianus to the right. The two ties of the laurel wreath are fluttering.

Rev. IMP HADRIAN DIVI NER TRAIAN OPT FIL

In the exergue: REST

Male figure, togate, standing to the front, looking left, sacrificing with his right hand on a lighted altar next to him, to the left.

RIC Hadrian 25A and *BMCRE* 3, p. 244, no. *, both with reference to Cohen (second edition), Trajan no. 663, where a coin of this type is mistakenly cited from the Paris collection: no such coin is to be found in the Bibliothèque nationale.²

Specimen 1

Vienna, Kunsthistorisches Museum, Münzkabinett, inv. RÖ 8705 (2.82g, 6h, max. diam. 19.9mm). **Pl. 15, 1 and 1a (200%)**.

Listed in the catalogue of Roman coins in the imperial cabinet by Arneth in 1842.³ Reference to this piece was made by Cohen (first edition)⁴ and by Strack – not in his catalogue proper, but in an appendix listing ‘Unbestimmbare Prägungen’.⁵

¹ Thanks for their help in preparing this article are due to Richard Abdy (London), William R. Day (Cambridge), Dominique Hollard (Paris), Klaus Vondrovec and Daniela Williams (both Vienna). I am most grateful to Andrew Burnett (London) for commenting on a previous draft.

² H. Cohen, *Description historique des monnaies frappées sous l'Empire Romain communément appelées médailles impériales*, second edition, vol. 2 (Paris – London, 1882), p. 88 (‘F’). Thanks are due to Dominique Hollard for confirming the absence of the type from the Paris collection.

³ I. Arneth, *Synopsis numorum romanorum qui in Museo Caesareo Vindobonensi adservantur* (Vienna, 1842), p. 83, Hadrian no. 25.

⁴ H. Cohen, *Description historique des monnaies frappées sous l'Empire Romain communément appelées médailles impériales*, vol. 2 (Paris – London, 1859), p. 86, no. 549 (‘Musée de Vienne’, with an estimate of 300 fr.).

⁵ P.L. Strack, *Untersuchungen zur römischen Reichsprägung des zweiten Jahrhunderts. Teil II: Die Reichsprägung zur Zeit des Hadrian* (Stuttgart, 1933), p. 230.

The coin is worn; the letters of the obverse legend bracketed in the description above are illegible, the OPT in the reverse legend is not clearly legible. The integration in the entry above has been made on the basis of the descriptions of *specimen 2* below.

This denarius was first described by Eckhel in vol. 6 of the *Doctrina numorum veterum*, published in 1796, who mentions that it was accessioned in Vienna ‘anno praesente’; it had been part of a hoard of (c.) 2,600 Roman imperial denarii discovered in the territory of ‘Neu-Cilli’ in southern Styria (‘Untersteiermark’), today Novo Celje, municipality of Žalec, Slovenia.⁶ In the archives of the Antikensammlung of the Kunsthistorisches Museum Vienna, a manuscript document pertaining to the acquisition of 221 silver coins from this hoard by the imperial coin cabinet could be located – alas, it does not contain specific descriptions of the individual pieces. The document is dated to 7 August 1795.⁷

Specimen 2

Formerly in the collections of Michelet d’Ennery (1709–1786) and Pascal-François-Joseph Gossellin (1751–1830); current whereabouts unknown. Technical data not available.

This specimen was first described in detail by Thomas Mangeart in 1763 (more than thirty years before *specimen 1* became known), when this coin was already in the d’Ennery collection.⁸ It was also mentioned as being in this collection in 1767 by Beauvais,⁹ and is listed in the 1788 d’Ennery auction catalogue as no. 1383.¹⁰ The coin then reappeared in 1864 in the sale catalogue of the collection of P.-F.-J.

⁶I. Eckhel, *Doctrina numorum veterum*. Vol. 6: *continens numos imperatorios a Iulio Caesare usque ad Hadrianum eiusque familiam* (Vienna, 1796), p. 441 (‘idem anno praesente gazae [...] Caesareae accessit repertus inter denarios imperatorios bis mille sexcentos in agro Novocileiensi Styriae’).

⁷Kunsthistorisches Museum Vienna, Antikensammlung, archives, no. 91/1795. I am grateful to Daniela Williams for pointing out this document to me. This hoard was not recorded by I.A. Mirnik, *Coin Hoards in Yugoslavia*. BAR International Series 95 (Oxford, 1981), nor by A. Miškec, ‘Hoards of the Roman period in Slovenia from the 2nd century BC to the 2nd century AD’, *Vjesnik Arheološkog muzeja u Zagrebu (VAMZ), third series* 45 (2012), pp. 379–90.

⁸Th. Mangeart, *Introduction à la science des médailles, pour servir à la connoissance des Dieux, de la religion, des sciences, des arts, et de tout ce qui appartient à l’histoire ancienne, avec les preuves tirées des médailles* (Paris, 1763), pp. 53f. : ‘Du nombre de celles [sc. des médailles restituées] rassemblées dans la même Collection [sc. de M. d’Ennery] il s’en trouve une qu’Hadrien fit frapper, après la mort de Trajan son prédécesseur, & son père adoptif [...]. Cette pièce, aussi authentique que rare, représente d’un côté la tête de Trajan couronnée de laurier, avec la légende *Divus Trajanus Pater Augustus*, & au revers, Hadrien lui-même debout près d’un Autel, sur lequel il offre un Sacrifice: on lit au tour IMP. HADRIAN. DIVI NER. TRAIAN. OPT. FIL., & dans l’exergue, REST.’

⁹G. Beauvais, *Histoire abrégée des Empereurs romains et grecs, des Impératrices, des Césars, des Tyrans, et des personnes des familles impériales pour lesquelles on a frappé des médailles [...]*, 3 vols (Paris, 1767), vol. 1, p. 211: ‘Il y a dans le Cabinet de M. d’Ennery une Médaille d’argent unique, restituée par Hadrien en l’honneur de Trajan après l’apothéose de ce Prince.’

¹⁰[Ch.-Ph. Champion de Tersan – P.-F.-J. Gossellin], *Catalogue des médailles antiques et modernes, principalement des inédites et des rares, en or, argent, bronze, etc. du cabinet de M. d’Ennery, Écuyer* (Paris, 1788), p. 334: ‘DIVVS TRAIANVS PATER AVGVSTVS. Tête de Trajan. IMP. HADRIAN. DIVI NER. TRAIAN. OPT. FIL. REST. Hadrien debout, sacrifiant sur un autel.’ The coin type is cited after this catalogue by I. Eckhel, *Doctrina numorum veterum*. Vol. 5: *continens numos consulares et familiarum* (Vienna, 1795), p. 100.

Gossellin,¹¹ one of the authors of the d'Ennery catalogue, who is known to have bought in the sale himself.¹² The description of this specimen in the Gossellin catalogue specifically states that the bust of Trajan on the obverse is with 'épaules nues';¹³ we thus may conclude that the bust variety of this denarius was the same as on the Vienna specimen.

Interest in the curious phenomenon of the restored coinages of the Principate has been constantly high since the Early Modern period, but scholarly activity has been particularly intense over the past two decades or so, which have seen an exceptional output of research on the topic. In 2001, Holger Komnick published an excellent monograph containing an attempt at a corpus as well as die-studies of the restored coinages of Titus, Domitian, Nerva and Trajan.¹⁴ In 2010, a new catalogue of all the restored issues of Trajan appeared in this author's handbook of Trajan's imperial coinage, in which Komnick's listing of the Trajanic restorations was systematically revised and updated, and a couple of previously unrecorded restored types were presented.¹⁵ In the previous volume of this journal Martin Beckmann published a die-study of the intriguing restored denarii copying Mark Antony's legionary issue (more precisely *RRC* 544/19), signed by M. Aurelius and Lucius Verus,¹⁶ thereby filling a gap that Komnick had left in his monograph. Moreover, a hitherto unrecognised restored denarius issue has recently been identified. Careful examination of a scarce variety of the well-known Augustan C. L. CAESARES denarii, catalogued by C.H.V. Sutherland as *RIC* Augustus 208, has made it clear that a re-attribution of these coins is necessary: scientific analyses show these denarii to have been produced from an alloy containing just about 80% of silver. In combination with observations on their typology, style and circulation behaviour, this indicates that we are dealing with an unsigned restoration of the High Principate, issued probably late in Hadrian's rule.¹⁷

The restored denarius issue honouring the Divus Traianus has not played a significant role in any of these studies from Komnick onwards, and for a simple reason: ever since the time of their discovery, scholars have been utterly baffled by the typology of these rare Hadrianic coins, which is why they frequently omitted

¹¹ *Catalogue des monnaies grecques et romaines composant la collection de feu M. P.-F.-J. Gossellin*. Auction catalogue Rollin et Feuarent, Paris, 7–12 March 1864, p. 46, no. 654 bis.

¹² See Th. Sarmant, *La république des médailles. Numismates et collections de numismatique à Paris du Grand Siècle au Siècle des Lumières* (Paris, 2003), p. 224.

¹³ 'DIVVS TRAIANVS PATER AVGVSTVS. Buste lauré de Trajan, les épaules nues. Rv. IMP. HADRIAN. DIVI NER. TRAIAN. OPT. FIL. REST. Hadrien debout sacrifiant près d'un autel.'

¹⁴ H. Komnick, *Die Restitutionsmünzen der frühen Kaiserzeit. Aspekte der Kaiserlegitimation* (Berlin – New York, 2001).

¹⁵ B. Woytek, *Die Reichsprägung des Kaisers Traianus (98–117)*. *Moneta Imperii Romani* 14, 2 vols (Vienna, 2010), nos 801–877. For dangerous modern forgeries of one Trajanic restored denarius type see B. Woytek, 'Kritische Bemerkungen zu einigen Restitutionen nach Denaren des republikanischen Münzmeisters L. Rubrius Dossenus (MIR 810)', *MÖNG* 56, no. 1 (2016), pp. 50–60.

¹⁶ M. Beckmann, 'The Restoration of Mark Antony's Legionary Denarii by Marcus Aurelius and Lucius Verus', *NC* 177 (2017), pp. 135–47. *RIC* Marcus Aurelius 443.

¹⁷ B.E. Woytek and M. Blet-Lemarquand, 'The C. L. CAESARES denarii *RIC* I² Augustus 208: A pseudo-Augustan unsigned restoration issue. Corpus, die study, metallurgical analyses', *RN* 174 (2017), pp. 183–248.

them from consideration altogether. Let us briefly lay out the problem. The so-called ‘restored’ coinages of the High Empire are by definition coins reproducing earlier coin types, normally with the addition of an inscription identifying the emperor(s) responsible for the restoration that ends in REST (i.e. *restituit* or *restituerunt*). The archetypal restorations, for that matter, are the restored denarii of Trajan. These are rare coins of a fine style that, with extremely few exceptions,¹⁸ copy their Roman Republican and Augustan prototypes most faithfully – not only their images, but also their inscriptions –, always with the additional legend IMP CAES TRAIAN AVG GER DAC P P REST on the reverse.

Yet, upon closer inspection it becomes evident that there was some flexibility in the design of restored coinages. Let us take the example of the rare restored denarii of Nerva, of which just five specimens are currently known.¹⁹ These coins were all struck from a single obverse die, featuring the bare head of the DIVVS AVGVSTVS. Three different reverse dies with different types were coupled with it. They show a bull butting to the right (**pl. 15, 2**), a comet with eight rays and a capricorn. These images are all attested on Augustan lifetime denarii, but not in combination with an obverse featuring the Divus Augustus, to be sure. Unlike the later denarius restorations of Trajan, the silver restorations of Nerva do not copy the reverse legends of their prototypes, but just feature the new reverse inscription IMP NERVA CAES AVG REST. Hence, already the moneymen of Nerva were not content with just copying what they found, but created new combinations of text and images.²⁰

The artists responsible for Trajan’s restored aurei were even more creative. Far from copying the prototypes slavishly (like the die-cutters of Trajan’s restored denarii), they often took even greater liberties than Nerva’s designers, as has repeatedly been observed.²¹ For most of the obverse-reverse combinations on imperial aureus restorations of Trajan there is no direct prototype. These coins are remarkable for the freedom with which the artists combined elements of different earlier coin types: these are sometimes, but not always drawn from the coinage of the emperor depicted on the obverse of the Trajanic restorations. For example, the winged Nemesis with a serpent, originally used on the precious metal coinage of Claudius, appears in combination with the Divus Iulius on the restoration of Trajan (**pl. 15, 3**). Most importantly in our context, the Divus Nerva, for whom Trajan had not issued any ‘regular’ commemorative imperial coinage,²² suddenly appeared on a restored aureus, coupled with the reverse image of an elephant biga drawing a cart with the statue of the Divus Nerva on it (**pl. 15, 4**). As I have suggested elsewhere, the reverse probably

¹⁸ Woytek, *Traianus*, nos 801–803.

¹⁹ See Komnick, *Restitutionsmünzen*, pp. 100f. and 231, with the addition of the specimen depicted on **pl. 15, 2**.

²⁰ See also Komnick, *Restitutionsmünzen*, pp. 143–5 on this point.

²¹ Komnick, *Restitutionsmünzen*, p. 145; see also M. Beckmann, ‘Trajan’s restored coinage: volume, value and purpose’, *RBN* 161 (2015), pp. 311–24, 312. In this paper Beckmann also points out further differences between Trajan’s restorations in gold and silver, especially regarding the quantities in which these two groups were produced, as compared to ordinary Trajanic issues in the two metals: relatively speaking, the restored aurei were much more prominent in the gold coinage of Trajan than the denarii in his silver.

²² See B.E. Woytek, ‘Divus Nerva. The coin evidence’, in: L. Bricault et al. (eds), *Rome et les provinces. Monnayage et histoire. Mélanges offerts à Michel Amandry*. Numismatica Antiqua 7 (Bordeaux, 2017), pp. 195–212, esp. 205.

takes its inspiration from contemporary Trajanic coins featuring the Diva Marciana;²³ what matters here is that there is no prototype for this combination of obverse and reverse image at all. This is another example of the engravers' creativeness; and in the case of Trajan's restored aurei the whole point of the exercise seems to have been to honour Caesar, the 'good emperors' and the *Divi Imperatores* up to Trajan.

In spite of this evidence, researchers dealing with the restored denarius of Hadrian in the name of Divus Traianus have desperately been looking for an immediate Trajanic prototype for centuries – but in vain: in all of Trajan's imperial coinage there is not a single denarius type featuring a man in a toga sacrificing at an altar. The only Trajanic reverse image of this kind occurs on dupondii of the utmost rarity, of which only two specimens are extant (**pl. 15, 5**):²⁴ they have never been considered in our context and may, indeed, in all probability be ruled out as prototypes.²⁵

Consequently, Eckhel had posited that this Hadrianic coin type was intended to commemorate Trajan in general, not to actually restore an earlier coin type, because he denied the existence of a prototype: '[sc. denarius] Hadriani restituit memoriam patris Trajani, cujus archetypon non extat'.²⁶ His words seem to echo Mangeart's judgement, according to whom this coin type was struck 'pour conserver plus particulièrement la mémoire de son Apothéose'.²⁷ Francesco Gnecci took the same line when he wrote: 'Il tipo non esiste fra le monete di Traiano. Pare che Adriano si sia piuttosto ispirato alle monete proprie, riproducendo il tipo di un suo denaro che porta la leggenda VOTA PVBLICA, e accompagnando colla propria figura sacrificante l'omaggio filiale d'una rievocazione dell'effigie paterna. A questa dunque unicamente si riferisce la restituzione.'²⁸ Hence, in Gnecci's opinion this would basically be just a restoration of the obverse portrait – a minimalist conception of a restoration indeed. Also, Gnecci's suggestion that the reverse reproduces that of Hadrian's own VOTA PVBLICA denarii (*RIC* 290) is not completely satisfying from the typological point of view, quite apart from serious chronological problems:²⁹ on the VOTA PVBLICA pieces, the emperor is shown sacrificing out of a patera over a tripod, not on an altar.

The situation apparently seemed confusing to Paul Strack, who decided to exclude the Vienna denarius from his catalogue and abstain from judgement altogether.³⁰ Harold Mattingly, writing just a couple of years after Strack, drily stated: 'The one coin with the restored formula on reverse [...] is quite anomalous'; he did not know what to make of the issue as such, either: 'it is quite uncertain what precisely is

²³ Reverse legend EX SENATVS CONSVLTO: Woytek, *Traianus*, nos 724–5 and p. 169. There is no hard and fast evidence for the traditional dating of the restored coins of Trajan to c. AD 107, recently advocated again by C.L. Clay, 'The Roman Imperial Coinage of Trajan', *NC* 172 (2012), pp. 347–62, 356f.

²⁴ Woytek, *Traianus*, no. 254 (Paris – shown on **pl. 15, 5** – and Milan).

²⁵ Also, there is a subtle iconographical difference between the two images, since the emperor sacrificing on Trajan's dupondii is shown *capite velato*, while the man on Hadrian's restored denarius is not.

²⁶ Eckhel, *Doctrina*, vol. 5, p. 109.

²⁷ Mangeart, *Science des médailles*, p. 53.

²⁸ F. Gnecci, 'Appunti di numismatica romana XLIV. Sulle restituzioni', *RIN* 10 (1897), pp. 123–57, p. 155.

²⁹ Strack, *Hadrian*, pp. 185f.: these denarii are to be connected with Hadrian's *vicennalia* in AD 137, whereas the restored denarii must be much earlier – see below.

³⁰ Strack, *Hadrian*, p. 230: 'solange nicht ein besser erhaltenes Exemplar bekannt wird, läßt sich schwer über diese vereinzelt Restitutionsmünze Hadrians urteilen.'

restored.³¹ In view of Mattingly's authority doubts were raised, in the wake of the publication of his third volume of *BMCRE*, as to whether Hadrian's restored denarius really was a restoration like all the others, from Titus to Trajan and beyond, or rather a mysterious separate phenomenon of some kind. For example Holger Komnick was extremely cautious and mentioned the Vienna denarius only in a footnote of his monograph, carefully describing it not as a restoration proper, but merely (in translation) as 'a type also with the word REST in the reverse legend'.³²

In fact, despite the perplexity of previous scholars since Eckhel, this denarius type of Hadrian can be shown to have been modelled on an ordinary denarius of Trajan. However, Hadrian's die engravers not only replaced the legends on both sides, but also slightly adapted the reverse image, which has so far prevented the prototype's identification. The reverse was copied from a Trajanic reverse type featuring the personification of Pietas, standing to the left in a long garment, with a sceptre in her left arm, sacrificing with her right hand on a lighted altar standing next to her, to the left. This reverse type was used in three successive issues of Trajan from the final phase of the fifth to the beginning of the sixth consulates, c. AD 111–112, with the titular dates COS V (see **pl. 15, 6** and **6a**),³³ COS V DES VI³⁴ and COS VI³⁵ respectively. Since the legends of the prototype were not copied on the Hadrianic coin,³⁶ it is difficult to know precisely which of these varieties served as the model of the restorations. Also, the bust type copied is a priori not completely clear: the bust of the Divus Traianus does not have a drapery, but it seems to be depicted, somewhat awkwardly, rather in a half-frontal perspective, for which there is no precise equivalent among the busts on the prototype issues in question. Perhaps a half-frontal bust with a paludamentum on the left shoulder, as shown in **pl. 15, 6** and **6a** (maybe on a worn specimen), was misinterpreted by the engraver cutting the obverse die for the restored denarius type? For what it is worth, one may observe that on the COS VI denarii of this type such a bust (Woytek bust d) has not so far been attested, so that the COS VI-variety is probably unlikely to have been the prototype. By contrast, such a half-frontal bust with a cloak on the left shoulder is known for both the COS V and COS V DES VI-varieties of the type.³⁷

These issues of Trajanic coins are characterised by the use of short additional legends on the reverse, describing the scene or naming the deities or personifications depicted in an abbreviated form. In the case of the Pietas denarii, the descriptive legend is PIET, in the exergue. These Pietas coins are the only Trajanic denarius type with a legend in the exergue that features one standing figure sacrificing at an altar. In the Hadrianic restoration, the four letters PIET were replaced by the four letters REST, again in the exergue: this detail alone immediately seems to reveal

³¹ *BMCRE* 3, p. cxxvii.

³² Komnick, *Restitutionsmünzen* p. 4, note 12: '[es] ist für Hadrian ein einzelner Denartyp bekannt, der ebenfalls das Wort REST in der Rückseitenlegende trägt'.

³³ Woytek, *Traianus*, no. 348.

³⁴ Woytek, *Traianus*, no. 379.

³⁵ Woytek, *Traianus*, no. 391.

³⁶ The inscriptions in the round on both obverse and reverse of the prototype coin, containing Trajan's lifetime name and titlature, plus SPQR OPTIMO PRINC(IPI), were replaced by the then current name of Divus Traianus and by the indication of who restored the coin on the reverse.

³⁷ Woytek, *Traianus*, nos 348d (8 specimens listed) and 379d (1 specimen listed). Overall, however, the reverse type is decidedly more common with the COS V date (41 specimens listed, as compared to just 14 for COS V DES VI).

the prototype. The ‘architectonics’ of the reverse³⁸ were left unchanged, just the protagonist was substituted. A man in the toga, who doubtless is to be identified as the new emperor Hadrian, piously offering sacrifice to his adoptive father depicted on the obverse,³⁹ took the place of Pietas.

This adaptation of the reverse image is, of course, significant in an ideological perspective. The message inherent in the substitution of Pietas ties in very well with what we know about political mass communication in the early days of Hadrian’s rule. As is well known, Hadrian was the provincial legate of Syria at the time of Trajan’s death; his *dies imperii* was 11 August 117, on which day he was hailed emperor in Antioch on the Orontes. Bitter rumours surrounded Hadrian’s alleged adoption by Trajan on the latter’s deathbed. They prompted the officials responsible for Hadrian’s initial issue of gold and silver coins at the mint of Rome to specifically highlight the event with a type featuring two *togati* on the reverse (Hadrian and the Divus Traianus), partly with the blatant legend ADOPTIO in the exergue.⁴⁰ Apparently, the latter type had been struck without consulting the new emperor; it obviously was not to his taste and was therefore soon discontinued. Apart from this type, the first issue comprised five more traditional denarius types that were, unlike the ADOPTIO coins, carried over into subsequent issues, too, and thus struck until AD 118. These were FORTuna REDux, supposed to get the new ruler home safely, and the personifications of four key values of the new regime, all identified in legends in the exergue or in the fields: CONCORDia and IVSTITIA, both seated to the left, and PAX as well as PIETAS (pl. 15, 7), both standing to the left.⁴¹

Among these four personifications Pietas – one of the core virtues of Roman emperors⁴² – held a prominent place. In the specific context of an imperial accession, Pietas often denoted a new ruler’s devotion to his (deified) predecessor.⁴³ In Hadrian’s case, this value was firmly tied to Hadrian’s filial piety in supporting his adoptive father’s immediate consecration,⁴⁴ as well as to his humble refusal to celebrate the

³⁸ For the expression ‘Architektonik des Münzbildes’, see R. Göbl, *Antike Numismatik*, 2 vols (Munich, 1978), vol. 2, pl. 131.

³⁹ That the emperor in the toga is shown sacrificing *aperto capite* – not *velato* – on our denarius may seem surprising at first sight, but is not without parallel: see F. Schmidt-Dick, *Typenatlas der römischen Reichsprägung von Augustus bis Aemilianus*, vol. 2: *Geographische und männliche Darstellungen* (Vienna, 2011), pp. 280f. and pl. 54, where examples from the imperial coinage of Domitian and Severus Alexander are illustrated. To these may be added a group of specimens of the Hadrianic denarius type VOTA PVBLICA, cited above (*RIC* 290; Strack, *Hadrian*, no. 288); contrary to the description in the current handbooks, the emperor is sometimes shown *aperto capite* on this type, too: see, e.g., Lanz 106 (27 November 2001), no. 421 (3.31g), or Gitbud & Naumann 26 (14 December 2014), no. 570 (3.27g), as well as several other specimens that have recently passed through the coin trade.

⁴⁰ Strack, *Hadrian*, nos 1–2 (the latter signed ADOPTIO). See O. Hekster, *Emperors and Ancestors. Roman Rulers and the Constraints of Tradition* (Oxford, 2015), p. 60: ‘The doubts surrounding Hadrian’s adoption may have caused the need for overcompensation’.

⁴¹ Strack, *Hadrian*, nos 3–7. Pietas is here depicted with her right arm raised, not offering sacrifice at an altar.

⁴² See C.F. Noreña, *Imperial Ideals in the Roman West. Representation, Circulation, Power* (Cambridge, 2011), pp. 71–7.

⁴³ On this aspect, see Noreña, *Imperial Ideals*, pp. 75f., and Hekster, *Emperors and Ancestors*, p. 86.

⁴⁴ The *Historia Augusta* reports that Hadrian wrote a letter to the senate from Syria to that effect; see HA Hadr. 6.1: *Traiano divinos honores datis ad senatum et quidem accuratissimis litteris postulavit et cunctis volentibus meruit, ita ut senatus multa, quae Hadrianus non postulaverat, in Traiani honorem sponte decerneret*. See J. Fündling, *Kommentar zur Vita Hadriani der Historia Augusta*. *Antiquitas* Reihe 4, Serie 3, vols 4.1–2 (Bonn, 2006), vol. 1, pp. 439f. on this passage.

triumph that the senate had transferred to him from Trajan: Hadrian preferred to reserve this honour to the dead Traianus Parthicus, ‘so that the best of emperors should not even after his death lose the solemn right to triumph’.⁴⁵ It is not only the personification of Pietas on the denarii which is to be connected with Hadrian’s filial piety towards Trajan,⁴⁶ but also one of the most remarkable aureus types of the Principate, issued in Rome in AD 117/118: on its reverse, a radiate phoenix is depicted, without any inscription (**pl. 15, 8**). This fabulous bird, associated with the sun, is not only the symbol of eternity, but also of the piety extending from one generation to another. According to ancient tradition, at the end of its life cycle the phoenix burns itself on a pyre, and from its ashes the next phoenix rises. The new bird’s foremost duty is to give burial to the remains of its parent, on the altar of the sun⁴⁷ – hence the connection with the piety of Hadrian towards Trajan.⁴⁸

Hadrian’s restored denarius type may be seen to have continued, on a new level, the creative approach in the design of restored coins already in evidence under Nerva and Trajan (for the aureus restorations). The coin was designed with the utmost care and perspicacity, presumably by somebody well acquainted with the intentions of the ‘propaganda’ of the day. By taking the place of Pietas in this coin image, the new emperor almost seems to become an embodiment of this virtue himself, which adds an extra dimension to the restored denarius type – at least for those (few?) viewers who were able to piece together the visual puzzle. But, whether or not the deeper meaning of the type was grasped, never before and never after was an imperial restoration designed in such a playful way.

Two points remain to be discussed briefly: the chronology and attribution of the issue and its relationship to the other restored coin types of Hadrian’s rule. On early aurei of Hadrian’s principate struck at the mint of Rome the Divine Trajan’s name appears in three different varieties.⁴⁹ On aurei combining his bust on the reverse with Hadrian’s bust on the obverse, the reverse inscription is either **DIVO TRAIANO PATRI (pl. 15, 9)**⁵⁰ or **DIVO TRAIANO PATRI AVG (pl. 15, 10)**,⁵¹ on these earliest coins, apparently struck during the first weeks of the new reign, Hadrian himself

⁴⁵HAHadr. 6.3: *cum triumphum ei (sc. Hadriano) senatus, qui Traiano debitus erat, detulisset, recusavit ipse atque imaginem Traiani curru triumphali vexit, ut optimus imperator ne post mortem quidem triumphum amitteret dignitatem*. The date of this posthumous triumph has caused some controversy in scholarship. W. Weber, *Untersuchungen zur Geschichte des Kaisers Hadrianus* (Leipzig, 1907), p. 65, and W. Kierdorf, ‘Apotheose und postumer Triumph Trajans’, *Tyche* 1 (1986), pp. 147–56, p. 153, place it in the autumn of AD 117, while Fündling, *Kommentar*, vol. 1, p. 442, A.R. Birley, *Hadrian. The Restless Emperor* (London – New York, 1997), pp. 99f., and D. Kienast, W. Eck and M. Heil, *Römische Kaisertabelle. Grundzüge einer römischen Kaiserchronologie. 6., überarbeitete Auflage* (Darmstadt, 2017), p. 117, date the triumph to the period after Hadrian’s return to Rome on 9 July 118.

⁴⁶Compare, e.g., Strack, *Hadrian*, pp. 51–4, and Mattingly in *BMCRE* 3, p. cxxv.

⁴⁷See Tacitus, ann. 6.28 (cf. 6.28.5: *et primam adulto curam sepeliendi patris*). The phoenix is expressly described as *pius* by Ovid, *Met.* 15.405, on which see F. Bömer, *P. Ovidius Naso. Metamorphosen. Kommentar; Buch XIV–XV* (Heidelberg, 1986), pp. 355–62, esp. 361. See also Lactantius, *de ave Phoenice* 122.

⁴⁸For the interpretation of the reverse, see Strack, *Hadrian*, pp. 55f. and Mattingly in *BMCRE* 3, pp. cxxvii f.

⁴⁹On these types, see also A. Burnett, ‘The early coinage of Hadrian and the deified Trajan at Rome and Alexandria’, *AJN, second series* 20 (2008), pp. 459–77, esp. 467–9.

⁵⁰Strack, *Hadrian*, no. 9.

⁵¹Strack, *Hadrian*, nos 10–12.

is given the names of Optimus, Germanicus, Dacicus and Parthicus which he had ‘inherited’ from his predecessor, but then decided not to bear, and which are therefore dropped from his titulature on coins from the second issue onwards.⁵² The aurei with the phoenix on the reverse, discussed above, belong to a somewhat later phase. Just like, e.g., the spectacular aurei featuring the TRIVMPHVS PARTHICVS on the reverse (**pl. 15, 11**),⁵³ these gold coins show the obverse legend DIVO TRAIANO PARTH AVG PATRI,⁵⁴ thus including the *cognomen ex virtute* Parthicus that Trajan had been awarded in AD 116. ‘Divus Traianus Parthicus’ was to remain the full form of the name henceforth,⁵⁵ although on a coin type with a terminus post quem of AD 123 (death of Plotina), Trajan’s portrait is accompanied by the shorter inscription DIVO TRAIANO AVGVSTI PATRI again.⁵⁶

Unfortunately, the obverse legend of the Vienna specimen of the restored denarius type is not completely legible. However, DIVVS TRAIANVS PA is absolutely clear, and traces of the two following letters TE seem to vindicate the reading unanimously reported for the d’Ennery specimen in the 18th and 19th century literature, viz. DIVVS TRAIANVS PATER AVGVSTVS. This form of the name links our denarii with the early aurei produced at the mint of Rome in honour of the new god in the late summer or early autumn of AD 117, as described above. The reverse legend of the restored denarii gives Hadrian’s name in the form IMPERATOR HADRIANVS DIVI NERVAE TRAIANI OPTIMI FILIUS. It also points to an early date in Hadrian’s reign: at the mint of Rome, the filiation occurs only in the legends of the first two issues of the precious metal coinage, as defined by Strack, hence in the first three months or so of Hadrian’s rule in AD 117.⁵⁷

However, one must not hastily attribute the restored denarii precisely to this period, too, since the closest numismatic parallel to their reverse inscription is to be found on rare provincial denarii of Hadrian in the style of Antioch on the Orontes,⁵⁸ struck at that mint in the following year, AD 118, when Hadrian held his second consulship. These coins bear the obverse legend IMP CAES HADRIAN DIVI NERVAE TRAIANI OPTIMI FILIUS, accompanying Hadrian’s portrait. Their reverse legend, containing the date, is unusual: AVG GER DAC PAR P M TR P COS ITERO (sic!) SPQR.⁵⁹ Currently, two reverse types coupled with this obverse are known, viz. Virtus standing to the right (**pl. 15, 12**)⁶⁰ and Fortuna Redux seated to the left (**pl. 15, 13**).⁶¹ Both pieces are unique. The reverse typology of Hadrian’s Antioch denarii that have been published

⁵² See the lucid analysis by Strack, *Hadrian*, p. 3.

⁵³ On the problems of dating, see n. 45 above; the numismatic evidence favours the earlier date.

⁵⁴ Strack, *Hadrian*, nos 21–24.

⁵⁵ Kienast, Eck and Heil, *Kaisertabelle*, p. 117.

⁵⁶ Strack, *Hadrian*, no. 357.

⁵⁷ Strack, *Hadrian*, pp. 3f.

⁵⁸ On which see, in general, R. McAlee, *The Coins of Roman Antioch* (Lancaster – London, 2007), pp. 216f.

⁵⁹ On the rare form *itero* (for *iterum*), see already the remarks by J. Eckhel, *Sylloge I numorum veterum anecdotorum Thesauri Caesaris cum commentariis* (Vienna, 1786), pp. 101f., as well as the funerary inscription *CIL VI 7578* (from Rome; AD 126).

⁶⁰ Strack, *Hadrian*, no. *5: Kunsthistorisches Museum Vienna, inv. RÖ 8721 (2.54g, 5h).

⁶¹ Dix Noonan Webb (London), auction sale [125] 22 September 2014, no. 3544 (2.96g). I am very grateful to Richard Abdy for bringing this specimen to my attention and for discussing the problem of attribution of the restored denarius with me.

so far is, without exception, purely derivative, and in a very unimaginative way. While most of these pieces copy contemporary denarii of Hadrian from the mint of Rome, these two coins are different. The letters 'SPQR' at the end of their reverse legend indicate that they were modelled on denarii of Trajan instead whose precious metal coins are characterised by this formula in the very same position, after Trajan had been awarded the name 'Optimus' in AD 114.⁶² Virtus was, just as Fortuna Redux, a very common Trajanic denarius type of the final years of his reign:⁶³ both images were of course highly suitable for the period of the Parthian campaign.

Hence, there are three closely related early Hadrianic denarius types, two of which – struck at Antioch – directly copy Trajanic denarius reverses; the third is a restoration inspired by a Trajanic denarius. What to make of this curious coincidence? All the other restored denarius issues of the High Principate we know of, from Nerva to Marcus Aurelius, were produced at the mint of Rome. Is it conceivable to assign an ingeniously designed restored issue to the mint of Antioch, whose other denarii are purely derivative in their typology? One cannot help but observe that Trajan's bust on the obverse of the restored denarius is somewhat clumsily engraved and has an unusual shape, as pointed out, which might tie in well with an attribution to the east. Also, it would seem more than hazardous to split up the group of three related Hadrianic denarius types, all clearly copied from Trajan denarii (directly or indirectly), by attributing the restored issue to a different mint. The fact that the only provenance of the restored issue is western – the Vienna coin was found in modern day Slovenia, as mentioned above – is not significant in the case of imperial precious metal issues.⁶⁴ Hence, this denarius type in the name of the Divus Traianus should be attributed to Syria. We must bear in mind that this does not make it the first restored issue to be assigned to a mint outside Rome: some of the bronze restorations of Titus and these of Domitian have been attributed to the mint producing imperial issues in Thrace (?), although the evidence is not easy to interpret.⁶⁵

As for the date of the restored issue, it does not seem possible to pin it down more precisely than 'late AD 117–118'; AD 118 is most likely, however, in view of the COS ITERO dating of the two related denarii with Hadrian's portrait from the mint of Antioch. This date would tie in very well with the date of the only appearance of the (Divus) Traianus on Roman provincial coins under Hadrian. His bust is famously featured on the reverse of two types of very rare tetradrachms of Alexandria in Egypt, dated to Hadrian's year 2.⁶⁶ These tetradrachms were struck in the first half

⁶² Cf. Woytek, *Traianus*, p. 147 and A. Burnett, 'Trajan Optimus' in: L. Bricault et al. (eds), *Rome et les provinces. Monnayage et histoire. Mélanges offerts à Michel Amandry*. Numismatica Antiqua 7 (Bordeaux, 2017), pp. 213–24.

⁶³ See Woytek, *Traianus*, nos 524, 558 and 578 (Virtus) and nos 495, 526, 559 and 579 (Fortuna Redux).

⁶⁴ See C. Howgego, 'Coin circulation and the integration of the Roman economy', *JRA* 7 (1994), pp. 5–21, esp. p. 15 (silver), and C. Howgego, 'The circulation of the gold coinage of Vespasian struck in the East', in R. Bland and D. Calomino (eds), *Studies in Ancient Coinage in Honour of Andrew Burnett* (London, 2015), pp. 125–37.

⁶⁵ Cf. the discussion by A. Burnett, M. Amandry and I. Carradice in *RPC* 2, part I, p. 87, and I.A. Carradice and T.V. Buttrey in *RIC* 2.1 (second edition), pp. 182, 193f. and 256f. Komnick, *Restitutionsmünzen*, pp. 87–9 and 99, preferred to attribute all these restored bronzes to the mint of Rome; it seems that he was mistaken on that.

⁶⁶ *RPC* 3, 5066 (3 specimens) and 5067 (4 specimens). Both types bear unusual inscriptions; the legends on the reverses are AYT TPAIAN API CE ΓΕΡΜ ΔΑΚΙΚ ΠΑ (5066, without any indication of

(or the first two thirds) of AD 118 – hence relatively late, as compared to the early appearance of the Divus Traianus on aurei from the mint of Rome.⁶⁷ Perhaps he was featured on coins at Antioch around the same time as in Egypt.

Our new appreciation of the signed restored denarius issue of Hadrian in the name of the Divus Traianus completes the picture of the restored coinages of the High Principate. For a new general overview of pertinent imperial issues, see *Table 1*. Apparently, Hadrian had two different restored denarius issues produced, and both were very unusual. After a signed issue of Eastern origin, innovatively adapting a Trajanic denarius type, the mint of Rome seems to have struck, perhaps towards the end of Hadrian's reign,⁶⁸ the anonymously restored C.L. CAESARES denarii *RIC* Augustus 208, another most unorthodox issue. Finally, one may remember that Hadrian was also responsible for remarkable cistophori with the portrait of Augustus on the obverse, bearing the reverse legend HADRIANVS AVG P P REN (*RPC* 3, 1441–1442). The final word of this inscription is probably to be expanded to *renovavit*,⁶⁹ and the issue as such should be seen in the context of Hadrian's large-scale renewal of the silver coinage of the province of Asia, by overstriking the much-worn cistophori mainly of the Late Republican and Augustan periods.⁷⁰ These unusual coins, which were already understood as 'restored' cistophori by Francesco Gnechi,⁷¹ may perhaps be interpreted as a provincial counterpart to Hadrian's two imperial denarius restorations. All told, this emperor was a somewhat more prolific issuer of restored coinages than hitherto suspected.

Issuer	Aurei	Denarii	Aes
Titus			X
Domitian			X
Nerva		X	X
Trajan	X	X	
Hadrian		X	
Anonymous restoration struck under Hadrian (C. L. CAESARES)		X	
Marcus Aurelius and Lucius Verus		X	

Table 1: Signed and unsigned restored imperial issues of the Roman Principate

the divinization!) and ΘΕΟ ΤΡΑΙΑΝΟC CEBACTOC ΠΙΑΤ ΚΥ (5067). On the latter inscription, see Burnett, 'The early coinage of Hadrian', p. 474.

⁶⁷ On the dating, see A. Burnett in *RPC* 3, p. 845, as well as Burnett, 'The early coinage of Hadrian', pp. 472–5. The Divus Trajan's comparatively late appearance on Egyptian coins is all the more intriguing since his consecration seems to have been known in Egypt at a very early point in time: Trajan is already called θεός on the papyrus P.Oxy. LV 3781, the copy of a document announcing Hadrian's accession that dates to 25 August 117.

⁶⁸ See Woytek and Blet-Lemarquand, 'C. L. CAESARES', p. 228.

⁶⁹ Thus, most recently, M. Amandry and A. Burnett in *RPC* 3, pp. 176 and 848. Hekster, *Emperors and Ancestors*, p. 174, n. 26, who prefers 'renovator', should not be believed.

⁷⁰ As correctly seen already by W.E. Metcalf, *The Cistophori of Hadrian*. Numismatic Studies 15 (New York, 1980), pp. 89f.; *pace* A. Mlasowsky, 'Eine neue Deutung zum Kistophor mit der Umschrift HADRIANVS AVG P P REN', *JNG* 61 (2011), pp. 85–107, and Hekster, *Emperors and Ancestors*, p. 174, n. 26.

⁷¹ Gnechi, 'Restituzioni', pp. 154f.; see also the discussion in F. Gnechi, 'Appunti di numismatica romana XLV. Contribuzioni al *Corpus numorum*. Collezione già William Boyne a Firenze ora F. Gnechi a Milano', *RIN* 11 (1898), pp. 43–59, esp. pp. 50–3.

Illustrations

- 1 Hadrian, restored denarius (Divus Traianus); *RIC* 25A; Vienna, Kunsthistorisches Museum, Münzkabinett, inv. RÖ 8705 (2.82g, 6h). Photo © Klaus Vondrovec. <<http://ikmk.at/object?id=ID60815>>
- 1a As no. 1, at 200%.
- 2 Nerva, restored denarius (Divus Augustus), Rome; Komnick, *Restitutionsmünzen*, Nerva no. 3.0; Helios 4 (14 October 2009), no. 233 (3.29g).
- 3 Trajan, restored aureus (Divus Iulius), Rome; Woytek, *Traianus*, no. 852–1; CNG Triton 19 (5 January 2016), no. 2188 (7.22g, 7h; ex H. Platt Hall).
- 4 Trajan, restored aureus (Divus Nerva), Rome; Woytek, *Traianus*, no. 873; CNG Triton 19 (5 January 2016), no. 2195 (7.31g, 6h).
- 5 Trajan, dupondius, Rome; Woytek, *Traianus*, no. 254a; Paris, Bibliothèque nationale, Cabinet des médailles: P.-A Besombes, [Bibliothèque nationale de France.] *Monnaies de l'Empire romain IV. Trajan (98–117 après J.-C.)* (Paris – Strasbourg, 2008), no. 593 (13.00g; 5h).
- 6 Trajan, denarius, Rome; Woytek, *Traianus*, no. 348d; Amsterdam, De Nederlandsche Bank, National Numismatic Collection (NNC), Heinrich Schürmann coll., inv. 335 (3.20g, 8h). Photo © Franziska Schmidt-Dick.
- 6a As no. 6, at 200%.
- 7 Hadrian, denarius, Rome; Strack, *Hadrian*, no. 7; *RIC* 8c; Gorny & Mosch 229 (10 March 2015), no. 1697 (3.41g).
- 8 Hadrian, aureus, Rome; Strack, *Hadrian*, no. 24; *RIC* 28 corr. (obv. legend and bust); CNG 94 (18 September 2013), no. 1167 (6.99g, 6h).
- 9 Hadrian, aureus, Rome; Strack, *Hadrian*, no. 9; *RIC* 23; Israel Museum Jerusalem, inv. 2016.015.36030 (7.08g, 6h): H. Gitler and G. Gambash (eds), *Faces of Power. Roman Gold Coins from the Victor A. Adda Collection* (Jerusalem – Zurich – London, 2017), pp. 210 and 306, VAC no. 164.
- 10 Hadrian, aureus, Rome; Strack, *Hadrian*, no. 10; *RIC* 24b corr. (obv. legend); NAC 67 (17 October 2012), no. 145 (7.39g; ex de Quelen).
- 11 Hadrian, aureus, Rome; Strack, *Hadrian*, no. 22; *RIC* 26 corr. (obv. legend); British Museum, *BMCRE Hadrian* 47 (7.24g, 6h). Photo © The Trustees of the British Museum.
- 12 Hadrian, denarius, Antioch; Strack, *Hadrian*, no. *5; Vienna, Kunsthistorisches Museum, Münzkabinett, inv. RÖ 8721 (2.54g, 5h, 17.8mm). Photo © Klaus Vondrovec. <<http://ikmk.at/object?id=ID60831>>
- 13 Hadrian, denarius, Antioch; unlisted in the reference works; Dix Noonan Webb (London) [125] 22 September 2014, no. 3544 (2.96g).

WOYTEK, THE PIOUS SON. ON THE RESTORED DENARIUS ISSUE SIGNED BY HADRIAN

